

STUDIES ON ENZYMES IN THE SYNTHESIS OF NICOTINE ALKALOIDS IN TOBACCO PLANTS

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In a previous communication (Bose *et al.*, *Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1956, **44**, 81), the effect of inorganic nitrogenous sources and various amino-acids on the synthesis of nicotine alkaloids in *Nicotiana tabacum* was reported. It was shown that the different tissues of the tobacco plants possessed capacity to synthesise nicotine from simple substrates like potassium nitrate, ammonium sulphate, tryptophane, proline etc. Klein and Linser (*Planta*, 1933, **20**, 470) and Dawson (*Plant Physiol.*, 1939, **14**, 479), in their feeding experiments with excised tobacco leaves, have also observed nicotine synthesis from various amino-acids. It is therefore of interest to investigate, if alkaloids, like nicotine, could also be synthesised *in vitro*, from its precursors or the process can be accelerated with the help of isolated enzyme preparations from tobacco leaves.

The enzymes from leaves, roots and stems of *N. tabacum* and *N. glauca* were extracted by grinding the tissues (10 g.) with 30 c.c. of distilled water at 3° and salting out by cold acetone (5°) after constant stirring. The enzyme, thus precipitated, was dried *in vacuo* and used for incubation with different substrates in a suitable aqueous medium containing magnesium and sodium sulphates, potassium chloride, calcium dihydrogen phosphate and sucrose in distilled water.

Different concentrations of potassium nitrate (0.1-10 mg.), amino-acids (tryptophane, proline, ornithine, arginine and anthranilic acid), riboflavin and nicotinic acid were incubated as substrates with the enzyme preparations with or without the tissue slices for 24 hours at 37°. The total nicotine synthesised was then distilled off with steam and collected in a receiver containing 5 c.c. of dilute hydrochloric acid. Nicotine content of the distillate was estimated by the cyanogen bromide and aniline colorimetrically, as detailed previously (Bose *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1956, **33**, 131).

From the first sets of experiment, it was observed that potassium nitrate appreciably increased the nicotine content from 0.23 μ g.-0.36 μ g., but there was no further enhancement of this synthesis due to addition of isolated enzyme preparations.

As the amino-acids, tryptophane, proline and ornithine, took active part in the *in vitro* synthesis of nicotine by the tissues of tobacco plant (Bose *et al.*, *loc cit.*), a second set of experiments was carried out to investigate whether the isolated enzyme preparations could react with the amino-acid precursors of nicotine synthesis. Incubation of enzyme preparations, isolated from different tissues of tobacco plants, with the substrate medium containing graded doses of amino-acid precursors was, however, found to be ineffective for the synthesis of nicotine alkaloid.

The nicotine synthesis could not be stimulated by adding riboflavin, niacin in the medium containing tryptophane and enzyme extract.

From the different series of investigations, carried out from this laboratory on the biogenesis of nicotine alkaloids, it has been observed that the synthesis of nicotine is accelerated by the addition of amino-acids and inorganic nitrates in *in vitro* as well as *in vivo* experiments. This synthesis, however, is not affected by further addition of isolated enzymes or factors like riboflavin and nicotinic acid.

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